

SUMMARY THE POSSIBILITIES OF NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL CORRECTION OF IMMUNOLOGICAL DISORDERS IN THE ACUTE PERIOD OF ISCHEMIC STROKE

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Due to the high mortality rate after a stroke, which in Uzbekistan remains one of the highest in the world, the optimization of early stroke rehabilitation has acquired particular importance in recent decades. Moreover, in 68% of cases, the cause of death in patients who have had a stroke over the age of 60 is complications that join the main pathological process, while the immediate severity of a stroke is only 32%.

In order to study the effectiveness of reflexotherapy in correction of immunological disorders in an acute period of ischemic stroke, 45 patients were clinical and immunological examined (on the 2nd day of patients's stay in hospital and 15 days after the beginning of the course of early rehabilitation). In the main group of patients (30 people), whose basic complex of rehabilitation measures was optimized by the inclusion of reflexotherapy, there was a significant improvement in a number of indicators of cellular and humoral immunity: reduction of leukocytes in peripheral blood ($p < 0.05$), an increase in lymphocyte count ($p < 0.05$), relative and absolute values of T-lymphocytes (CD3+) content ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$, respectively), immunoregulatory cells of T-helpers (CD4+) ($p < 0.05$), decrease in the number of B-lymphocytes to normal values ($p < 0.01$), and an increase in IgG level ($p < 0.05$). In the control group (15 people), where standard treatment was conducted, there was no pronounced dynamics of the indices. Thus, a comprehensive clinical and immunological study of the effectiveness of non-drug correction of immunological disorders in the acute period of ischemic stroke demonstrated high efficiency of acupuncture, with relative simplicity and safety of its application.

References:

1. Bakunts G.O. Endogenous factors of cerebral stroke. M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2011. – P.360.
2. Vilensky B.S. Complications of stroke: prevention and treatment. St. Petersburg: Foliant, 2012. – P. 128 p.
3. Vilensky B.S. Stroke - the current state of the problem // Neurological Journal. 2008. T.13, No. 2.- P.4–10.